

Cosmic Microwave Background and Large Scale Structure Power Spectrum Estimation with Guided Hamiltonian Sampling

by

Suhail Dhawan

Supervisors: Dr. Filipe Abdalla, Dr. Sreekumar Balan

Department of Physics and Astronomy

University College London
Gower Street, London WC1E 6BT
United Kingdom

Email: s.dhawan.12@ucl.ac.uk

Tel: +44 (0)7523352382

19 August 2013

REPORT SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF MSc IN ASTRO-
PHYSICS IN THE UNIVERSITY OF LONDON

Abstract

Cosmological surveys return large datasets probing different epochs in the evolutionary history of the universe. It is therefore unfeasible to use brute force methods to analyse this data.

Aim: In this project, we test the applicability of the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler (GHS), a modified Monte Carlo (MC) sampling process on galaxy clustering data. We compare its performance and efficiency with conventional methods used for cosmic microwave background (CMB) and large scale structure (LSS) power spectrum estimation. We apply the sampler to observed data from surveys like SDSS, Dark Energy Survey etc.

Method: GHS suppresses the random walk nature of traditional MC sampling techniques by obeying the hamiltonian equations of motion in the sample space. It is an extension of the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC). It removes the need to fine-tune a million parameters in HMC and only requires a single parameter, the dimensionality scaling factor. This makes it an exciting method to use on higher dimensional datasets.

Result: After analysing sampler performance under various configurations and input parameters, we find that GHS returns fiducial values in the domain of high spatial galaxy population. Comparing it with conventional methods like pseudo C_l , we see that the error bars from the sampler are similar in magnitude. Using GHS on datasets like SDSS and DES, we confirm the excess of power observed on the largest scales in the literature (Thomas et al. [2011], Huterar et al. [2013]).

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisors Dr. Filipe Abdalla and Dr. Sreekumar Balan for their unending support during the year, without which this project would not be possible. I would like to extend my gratitude to Dr. Balan for his tutorials on C/C++ which helped in accelerating the progress of the project and in understanding the previously written routines.

I would like to thank the Inlaks Shivdasani Foundation for funding my MSc in astrophysics. The course and this thesis would not be possible without their generous support.

I would like to thank Laura Wolz for explaining the usage of her pseudo C_l code. The sections on pseudo C_l estimation and comparison of estimation methods would not be possible without her help. I would like to thank Dr. Alex Merson for his help with reading the BOSS CMASS sample catalogs.

I would like to thank Dr. Filipe Abdalla and Dr. Sreekumar Balan for reading this report and offering invaluable suggestions and corrections.

Contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	Nature of Data	6
1.2	Conventional Methods	7
1.2.1	Maximum Likelihood	7
1.2.2	Pseudo C_l	8
1.3	Bayesian Parameter Estimation	9
1.3.1	Bayes Theorem	9
1.3.2	Numerical Methods	10
1.4	Motivation	12
1.5	Thesis Outline	13
2	CMB analysis with Guided hamiltonian Sampler	14
2.1	Generating Simulated CMB maps	14
2.2	C_l estimation	15
2.2.1	Dealing with Masks	16
3	Generating Simulated Galaxy Clustering Data	18
3.1	Introduction	18
3.2	Method 1: Using Cumulative Distribution Function	19
3.3	Method 2: Generating a Poisson Distribution	20
3.4	Comparing the Methods	22

3.5	Analysis of Noise	23
3.5.1	Methods for Calculating $Z(1)$	25
3.5.2	χ^2 tests	26
3.6	Summary and Discussion	26
4	Analysis of Simulated Galaxy Clustering Data	29
4.1	Introduction	29
4.2	High Signal to Noise Data	30
4.2.1	Dealing with Data Masks	32
4.3	Low Signal to Noise Data	33
4.4	Comparing Estimation Methods	33
4.5	Summary and Discussion	34
5	Application of GHS to Cosmological Datasets	35
5.1	Introduction	35
5.2	MegaZ DR7 Data	36
5.2.1	Dealing with Masks	37
5.3	Estimation with MegaZ DR7 data	38
5.4	Analysis of Systematics	40
5.4.1	Systematics in GHS	41
5.5	Dark Energy Survey (DES)	41
5.5.1	Power Spectrum Estimation	42
5.6	BOSS mock data	42
5.7	BOSS Data Catalog and Angular Power Spectrum	44
5.8	Summary and Discussion	45
6	Conclusion	46
A	Theoretical Power Spectrum	48
B	Pseudo C_l Estimation	50

B.1 Dealing with Masks	51
C Bayesian Confidence Interval	52
References	

Chapter 1

Introduction

The discovery of anisotropy of the cosmic microwave background was one of the greatest scientific achievements of the last century. The group working with CMB maps from the COBE satellite, a dataset of ~ 4000 dimensions (Figure 1 shows the 4-year COBE power spectrum from Tegmark et al. [1996]), found temperature fluctuations of 1 part in 100000 from the mean temperature of 2.73K. This culminated in the award of the 2006 Nobel prize in physics to Professors John Mather and George Smoot. The nature of these fluctuations offers insight into conditions in the very early universe and the seeds of structure formation. A clear picture of early universe cosmology is emerging as a result of CMB probes. A review of CMB cosmology is presented in Challinor [2012], Hu and White [2004].

Galaxy redshift surveys are a powerful tool to measure a contrasting cosmic epoch (Peebles [1973]). They return a substantial amount of information about the large scale structure of the universe and its evolution through gravitational amplification from primordial perturbations. The two-point galaxy correlation function provides a test for standard inflation and different cosmological models that predict the observed structure of the universe. The large scale structure also has imprinted in it standard length scales which yield oscillatory features in the power spectrum, called Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO). Since the physics of BAO is well understood, this allows for an accurate distance redshift relation and an independent probe of the accelerated expansion of the universe.

Power spectra present valuable information about the nature of the fluctuations (CMB temperature or galaxy count) at different angular scales to offer poignant insights into the history of the universe and its structure on the large scales. They provide a compact form of a few coefficients to describe distribution of a large number of overdensities (temperature or galaxy). Estimated power spectra are also compared with their theoretical counterparts to accu-

rately constrain cosmological parameters from the observed data (Dunkley et al. [2009]).

Figure 1.1: The 4-year COBE power spectrum Tegmark [1996]. The blue region is the 1-sigma error bar. The vertical error bars account for the error from pixel noise as well as cosmic variance. The horizontal error bars reflect the width of the window function used. The dark shaded region shows the contribution from cosmic variance. We can see that the power spectrum only extends to about $l=30$.

1.1 Nature of Data

Both CMB and LSS data can be written as a sum of a signal \mathbf{s} and noise \mathbf{n}

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n} \quad (1.1)$$

the temperature \mathbf{t} can be mapped into the signal \mathbf{s} through the mapping \mathbf{R} .

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{t} + \mathbf{n} \quad (1.2)$$

Using the spherical harmonic decomposition from the angular solution to laplace's equation in spherical polar coordinates.

$$\mathbf{t}(x_p) = \sum_{l=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l a_{lm} Y_{lm} \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{Y}\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{n} \quad (1.4)$$

Where Y is the orthogonal basis vector and a is the spherical harmonic coefficient.

The elements of the covariance matrix are given by

$$C_{lm'l'm'} = \langle a_{lm} a_{l'm'} \rangle \quad (1.5)$$

Where the set of coefficients C_l defines the angular power spectrum and since the sky is real

$$a_{lm} = a_{l,-m}^* \quad (1.6)$$

For CMB datasets, both the signal and the noise are assumed to be realizations of independent Gaussian processes

$$\langle \mathbf{d}\mathbf{d}^T \rangle = \langle \mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^T \rangle + \langle \mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^T \rangle \quad (1.7)$$

Which can be written in matrix formulation as $\mathbf{D}=\mathbf{C}+\mathbf{N}$, where \mathbf{C} is the signal covariance matrix and \mathbf{N} is the noise covariance matrix. \mathbf{d} is the data vector.

1.2 Conventional Methods

1.2.1 Maximum Likelihood

This was the first method used in the early 90's for CMB power spectrum estimation with data from the COBE satellite. Maximum likelihood (Gorski 1994, Bond et al. [1998], Oh et al. [1999]) is an optimal and unbiased method for the estimation of the power spectrum from observed TOD. It is helpful in estimating the coefficients from interferometric experiments for the measurement of CMB anisotropies (Hobson and Maisenger [2002]).

The likelihood function is defined as the probability of observing data given a set of power spectrum coefficients.

$$L(C_l) = \Pr(\mathbf{d}|C_l) \quad (1.8)$$

Borrill [1998] explains the quadratic estimator for maximize the likelihood function. In order to rapidly search for the maximum of L

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial C_l} = 0 \quad (1.9)$$

is iteratively evaluated with the Newton Raphson method. In Tegmark et al. [1996], the COBE power spectrum is estimated by taking a weighted linear combination of all pixels, squaring it (as is shown in the relation between a'_{lm} s and C'_l s and subtracting noise. It is argued that if the power spectrum is

parametrized by a small number of parameters an effective likelihood analysis for estimation can be performed.

Since the calculation of the likelihood requires the inversion and multiplication of the covariance matrix which is of order $O(N_{pix}^3)$, where N_{pix} is the number of pixels, this method is not feasible for megapixel datasets like Planck or WMAP. There are approximations of the covariance matrix that reduce the order to $O(N_{pix}^2)$, however, the reduction is not sufficient and it also leads to loss of information and creeping in of bias since the low C_l s will be having low variance.

Maximum likelihood methods have been used in LSS analysis in studies like Huterar et al. [2001], Tegmark et al. [2002], Hayes et al. [2011].

1.2.2 Pseudo C_l

A power spectrum is the square of the Fourier transform of the density for a distribution in flat space and of the spherical harmonic transform of the density for a distribution in three dimensions. This method helps in establishing contamination of the pseudo-spectrum by irregularities in different parts of the actual spectrum. The method has been used for several CMB experiments like BOOMERANG (Jones et al. [2005]) and MAXIMA (Stompor et al. [2003]). A discussion of its application to CMB cosmology can be found in Hivon et al. [2002].

This method allows for the estimation of a pseudo-spectrum by using the spherical harmonic coefficients of the signal presuming noise-free, full sky coverage. It can be used for datasets of any size and is an efficient method; however it is not feasible at large scales (low multipoles). The C_l s can be estimated by:

$$C_l = \frac{1}{2l+1} \sum_m |a_{lm}|^2 \quad (1.10)$$

Emission from galactic foregrounds prevents us from having a full sky coverage. Survey strategy is also important since number of observations for different parts of the sky may vary. There is a significant contribution from detector noise and a convolution with an observing beam. In pseudo- C_l weights $w(\mathbf{x})$ are assigned to each position to encode not only the partial sky coverage, but also all other effects that cause a deviation from the ideal power spectrum. Thus, the equation now reads.

$$\tilde{C}_l = \frac{1}{2l+1} \sum_m |\tilde{a}_{lm}|^2 \quad (1.11)$$

Where \tilde{C}_l 's are the power spectrum coefficients derived from the partial

sky coverage. Pseudo C_l methods have been used for large scale structure analysis in studies like Thomas et al. [2010]. Blake et al. [2004], analyses the NVSS radio galaxy sample with both Maximum Likelihood and Pseudo C_l estimation, providing a clear comparison of the 2 methods.

1.3 Bayesian Parameter Estimation

Problems in physics mostly boil down to finding patterns in observations. These patterns are expressed as mathematical models. In order to discriminate between several different models we estimate the value of parameters contained by them. Bayes' theorem allows us make this estimate of a parameter or set of parameters given a dataset with the knowledge of the likelihood of having observed that data and the prior information we have about the parameter from the model. Bayesian inference has been used in several different areas of astronomy and astrophysics some of which are cosmic ray physics (Watson et al. [2011]), supernova cosmology (Mandel et al. [2011]), dark matter detection (Arina [2011]), gravity wave background from pulsar timing arrays (Lentati et al. [2012]) and even the search for exoplanets (Balan et al. [2008]).

In this section, we look at the fundamentals of Bayesian parameter estimation, the numerical methods (Mackay[2003] provides a review) for sampling the probability distribution of the parameter given the data and the tests for convergence of these numerical techniques. Trotta [2008] provides a holistic review of Bayesian parameter estimation.

1.3.1 Bayes Theorem

In cosmological data analysis we use a Bayesian outlook of assigning degrees of belief or 'weights' to a given proposition or value that a parameter can take. This approach was first introduced by Revd. Thomas Bayes in 1763 in his seminal article 'An essay towards solving a Problem in the Doctrine of Chances'. Bayes' theorem for estimating parameter Θ given data D and model H is written as

$$\Pr(\Theta|D, H) = \frac{\Pr(D|\Theta, H) \Pr(\Theta|H)}{\Pr(D|H)} \quad (1.12)$$

The theorem relates the posterior probability $\Pr(\Theta|D, H)$, the likelihood $\Pr(D|\Theta, H)$ and the prior knowledge $\Pr(\Theta|H)$. The Bayesian evidence $\Pr(D|H)$ is independent of the parameter Θ , we can treat it as a normalizing constant and write the above expression as

$$\Pr(\Theta|D, H) \propto \Pr(D|\Theta, H) \Pr(\Theta|H) \quad (1.13)$$

1.3.2 Numerical Methods

Metropolis-Hastings

The most common method used for sampling a posterior distribution is the Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm, posited independently in Metropolis et al. [1953] and Hastings[1970].It creates a sequence of points in parameter space whose density is proportional to the posterior distribution. Given initial state x_0 , a new proposed point x_1 drawn from a proposal distribution $Q(x_0, x_1)$ is accepted with probability.

$$A = \min\left[1, \frac{Pr(x_1)Q(x_1, x_0)}{Pr(x_0)Q(x_0, x_1)}\right] \quad (1.14)$$

If the proposal distribution is symmetric about x_1 and x_0 , $Q(x_1, x_0) = Q(x_0, x_1)$, A reduces to the ratio of the two probabilities. The process is repeated till enough samples are obtained for estimating the desired probability distribution.

Gibbs Sampling

Since the acceptance in the MH algorithm depends on the ratio of the probabilities, many of the points will be rejected. Gibbs sampling removes the need to reject points, thus, each one can be used to build the posterior. It is done by presuming prior knowledge of the conditional distributions of the parameters. A review of Gibbs sampler algorithm and its application to CMB data can be found in .

For a model with 2 parameters θ_1 and θ_2 , we wish to map $\Pr(\theta_1, \theta_2)$. We define a proposal distribution T for θ_2 as a conditional distribution

$$T(\theta_1^{i+1}, \theta_2^{i+1} | \theta_2^i, \theta_1^i) = \delta(\theta_1^{i+1} - \theta_1^i) \Pr(\theta_2^{i+1} | \theta_1^i) \quad (1.15)$$

Where the proposal is considered only for $\theta_1^{i+1} = \theta_1^i$, i.e. when θ_1 is fixed and θ_2 is varied. Applying the Metropolis Hastings acceptance criterion

$$A = \frac{T(\theta_1^{i+1}, \theta_2^{i+1} | \theta_2^i, \theta_1^i) \Pr(\theta_1^{i+1}, \theta_2^{i+1})}{T(\theta_1^i, \theta_2^i | \theta_2^{i+1}, \theta_1^{i+1}) \Pr(\theta_1^i, \theta_2^i)} \quad (1.16)$$

Enforcing the delta function such that $\theta_1^{i+1} = \theta_1^i$, sampling from the conditional distribution makes it such that the terms cancel out making

$$A = 1 \quad (1.17)$$

Hence one can alternate from known conditional distributions, where each step is independently accepted and can be performed as many times as needed.

Gibbs sampling was first used in CMB analysis in Wandelt et al. [2004] and has been used for estimation at low l 's with the WMAP7 data in Larsson et al. [2011]. Groeneboom [2009] provides a self-contained guide to the CMB Gibbs Sampler. In Kitaura et al. [2009], an algorithm ARES, based on Gibbs sampling was applied to mock data of the large scale structure. Lunn et al. [2000] summarizes the BUGS project, a package for Bayesian analysis of statistical models using Gibbs Sampling.

Hamiltonian Monte Carlo and GHS

The Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (Duane et al. [1978]) can be treated as a special way of proposing a new sample, i.e. with a different acceptance criterion. This technique for sampling is based on the equations from Hamiltonian dynamics.

$$H = \sum_i^N \frac{p_i^2}{2m} + \Psi(x) \quad (1.18)$$

where $\Psi(x)$ is the negative log of the posterior probability distribution

$$\Psi(x) = -\log \Pr(x) \quad (1.19)$$

The objective in the sampling methodology is the sample from a distribution which is proportional to $\exp(-H)$ and can be written as,

$$\exp(-H) \propto \Pr(x) \prod_i^N \exp\left(\frac{-p_i^2}{2m}\right) \quad (1.20)$$

From (x_0, p_0) as the initial starting point, the system is evolved deterministically to a new point in phase space (x_1, p_1) . This process follows

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} \quad (1.21)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial x_i} \quad (1.22)$$

The new point is accepted with the probability

$$p_A = \min(1, \exp(-\delta H)) \quad (1.23)$$

Where

$$\delta H = H(x_1, p_1) - H(x_0, p_0) \quad (1.24)$$

A leapfrog step for evolving (x_0, p_0) to (x_1, p_1) is repeated n times with a finite step size ϵ , so that the total evolution time is $T=n\epsilon$. In order to randomize

the phase space trajectories we draw n and ϵ from uniform distributions $U(1, N)$, $U(0, E)$ respectively, where N and E are the maximum values that the number of steps and the step size can take. This allows for a random variation of the evolution time T . HMC has been applied to CMB data in Taylor et al. [2008]. In Jasche et al. [2009], Hamiltonian sampling has been used for large scale structure mock data.

For our project, we wish to use the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler. The technique is outlined in Balan et al. [2012] and is summarized by the following steps:

1. Find the peak of the distribution
2. Calculate the Hessian of the negative log posterior at the peak
3. Perform eigen-decomposition of the Hessian and obtain the principal coordinates
4. Set step sizes as the inverse square root of the eigenvalues of the Hessian
5. Set the dimensionality scaling factor η , and sample in the principal coordinates
6. Calculate convergence statistics and stop once condition is met

GHS uses the Hessian of the negative log of the posterior at the peak to assign step sizes in the sampling process.

$$\mathbf{E} = \eta \mathbf{H}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1.25)$$

This removes the need to fine tune the sizes ϵ , thus, improving the efficiency in sampling higher dimensional posterior distributions.

1.4 Motivation

Over the years, cosmology has evolved into a field where brute force methods are not feasible for data analysis. With surveys returning high resolution maps of the universe, there is a pressing need for novel techniques to be implemented so that results are optimal, efficient and computationally feasible. Traditional methods for power spectrum estimation do not scale well with the resolution of the dataset, therefore making them computationally unfeasible. There is also a possibility of biases creeping in some estimates, which makes the methods sub-optimal. The aims of the project are as follows:

1. To apply a sampling method, GHS, which has been used on CMB data, to galaxy clustering data. This project presents the first such investigation with large scale structure data.

2. To apply sampling techniques to published and unpublished data, to estimate power spectra from observed galaxy catalogs.
3. To demarcate the regime in which the sampler works. This is useful for future surveys like EuCLID. Since there hasn't been any such study for EUCLID in the past, this is an exciting investigation.

We would also like to analyse the performance of the sampler with different input characteristics to argue its validity for application to current and future surveys like Dark Energy Survey (DES) and EuCLID. These investigations can then be used to glean information about the underlying cosmology from the surveys. Such tests for galaxy surveys have not been performed before.

1.5 Thesis Outline

The structure of the report is as follows. In Chapter 2, we apply GHS to CMB data as is done in Balan et al. [2012] and set up an interface to the sampler that can work with any input cosmology. We look at the sampler performance under different conditions.

In chapter 3, we move onto galaxy data by first introducing the methods for producing the simulated maps and comparing their results. In chapter 4, we analyse the simulated data using pseudo- C_l and GHS, comparing the two estimation techniques. Chapter 5 summarizes the application of GHS to observed galaxy catalogs like SDSS and DES. Chapter 6 is a short conclusion of the work undertaken.

Chapter 2

CMB analysis with Guided hamiltonian Sampler

Signals from the cosmic microwave background (CMB) are powerful probes of the early universe. They offer unique insights into the nature of fluctuations in the relic radiation from the big bang. Surveys like COBE produced low-resolution maps of the CMB with $n_{pix} \sim 4000$. The power spectra estimated from these maps extended upto a multipole of $l \sim 30$. Modern surveys of the CMB like Planck and WMAP return megapixel maps in several different frequency channels. The Planck power spectrum extends to l of a few thousand.

Since current datasets are extremely large, the task at hand involves creating and applying a computationally feasible estimation method which is optimal and unbiased. Traditionally, the CMB community has used Maximum Likelihood (ML) and pseudo C_l (PCL) methods for estimating the power spectra. Recently, sampling methods have been incorporated in the analyses since they provide unbiased estimates and are computationally efficient.

In this chapter we look at the application of GHS to simulated CMB data. In section 2.1, we provide a framework for generating the simulated maps from input cosmology (WMAP7, in this case). In section 2.2, we look at the estimation of C_l 's with different input characteristics.

2.1 Generating Simulated CMB maps

For the initial part of the analysis, we use fiducial power spectrum coefficients from the cosmological parameters obtained by WMAP7. We use this theoretical estimate as our starting point to generate signal realizations a_{lm} which are

related to the C_l 's as follows

$$C_l \delta_{ll'} \delta_{mm'} = \langle a_{lm} a_{l'm'} \rangle \quad (2.1)$$

To account for the aperture of the instrument, the map is convolved with a gaussian beam. The beam width is related to the size of the pixel.

$$FWHM_{radians} = 1.5 * 2 * \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{N_{pix}}} \quad (2.2)$$

where $2 * \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{N_{pix}}}$ is the pixel size. We can see that the full width at half maximum is inversely related to the total number of pixels (N_{pix}). Thus, with high resolution simulations, the beam convolved is smaller.

The resulting a_{lm} 's are converted into a temperature map using the HealPix **Alm2Map** functionality. This gives an array of temperature anisotropy values for each pixel in the map. In the low-resolution regime, this is a very quick process since the total number of pixels is $\sim 10^5$.

We model the noise as an isotropic, Gaussian process. The value of each element of the noise matrix is the average noise value of the WMAP W-band, σ_0

$$rms_{noise} = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{N}} \frac{N_{side}}{512} \quad (2.3)$$

N is the number of photons received by the detector. The second term is the ratio of the N_{side} to 512, the resolution for WMAP. This accounts for the pixelisation scheme used. From the formula we can see that the noise decreases as we receive more photons. Therefore, for an unmasked (i.e. full-sky simulation) the noise matrix is not complex. The noise is then added to the array containing temperature data and the map is saved as a *fits* file.

2.2 C_l estimation

For the estimation of C_l 's we use the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler described in the previous chapter. We make an $n_{side} = 16$ map with $l_{max} = 2 * n_{side}$. The beam FWHM is 0.05 radians and the rms Noise is 1μ K. The map has ~ 3000 pixels. We set η as 0.5. The sampler takes the noise, data, beam, a_{lm} 's and realisation power spectrum of the original input C_l as input parameters. For the given configuration, the sampler takes 3000 samples to converge with an acceptance rate of 0.9. The table summarizes the results with different parameters.

We see that the sampler converges even when the noise matrix is over- or under-estimated. However, this takes long if the input noise matrix for the sampler has different values from the noise in the simulated CMB maps.

Figure 2.1: The green line shows the theoretical values of the D_l 's. The blue points are the GHS estimates. The best estimate is given by the mean and the error is the standard deviation. $l_{max} = 2 * n_{side} = 64$

From the table we interpret that a smoothing of the data with wider beams requires the sampler to take longer for convergence. Since for a fixed n_{side} (and thus, fixed n_{pix}), the beam input into the map (and sampler), there is a direct relation to the beam width, the sampler drops in efficiency due to a mismatch between the inputs and the theoretical value of the width.

Next, we perform a similar analysis with the rms noise being input into the noise matrix N .

2.2.1 Dealing with Masks

The CMB signal is severely affected by the foreground emissions from our galaxy and point sources. Thus, data from these parts of the sky can't be used for cosmology. We need to mask pixels which represent these parts of the sky. The application of a mask produces correlations in the a'_{lm} s, decreasing the acceptance rate of the sampler and making the process of obtaining C_l 's longer.

Table 2.1: Variation of the sampler acceptance rate and total number of samples required with change in beam size. Resolution $n_{side} = 16$

Beam width (radians)	Acceptance Rate	Number of Samples
0.04	0.9	2900
0.05	0.9	2900
0.07	0.85	3100
0.1	0.8	4000
0.12	0.75	4500

Figure 2.2: Data mask for $n_{side} = 32$. The region accounts for emission from the Milky way.

For our analyses with low-resolution data, we use two types of masks. Firstly, we apply a general symmetric mask which truncates a certain region above and below the equator. Although, this doesn't model the galaxy as well as the WMAP data masks, it serves as a template to see the drop in sampler performance. After working with a symmetric mask of different sizes, we can then use the WMAP, KQ75 mask. Since the mask KQ75 isn't as straightforward as a symmetric truncation, we see that for the same input parameters, the sampler takes a longer time to converge for KQ75 mask.

Chapter 3

Generating Simulated Galaxy Clustering Data

3.1 Introduction

Galaxy redshift surveys offer unique insight into the late-time evolution of the universe. They breakdown parameter degeneracies from CMB probes. Galaxies are tracers of the underlying mass distribution whose statistical clustering enables us to determine a cosmological model. The galaxy correlation function from the APM survey showed one of the first signs of $\Omega_m < 1$, before supernovae from the High- z and SCP groups.

In this project, we aim to apply the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler to galaxy clustering data. In order to test its validity for large scale structure datasets we apply it to simulated data.

In this chapter we look at two methods for simulating galaxy maps, namely, generating a cumulative distribution function by random sampling and generating a Poissonian distribution. After describing both methods in detail, we compare the results and justify our choice for using the Poissonian variable generation for analysis of the estimation method in the next chapter.

For both methods for simulating data maps, we look at the efficacy for obtaining fiducial values using realisation power spectra. The aim of this test is to observe the accuracy of the method of simulation and confirm that estimation methods like GHS can be used on simulation obtained using either of the methods.

The aim of this chapter is to compare two methods for simulating galaxy clustering data and analyse the noise in the simulated maps.

The overview of the chapter is as follows. In sections 3.2 and 3.3, we introduce the two methods for generating the simulations. We look at the resulting power spectrum estimates from both methods and the overdensity maps produced. This lays the groundwork for the comparison between the two methods. In section 3.4 we compare the power spectra obtained from both the methods. Section 3.5 we analyse the noise in the simulated data maps. In section 3.6, we provide a summary

3.2 Method 1: Using Cumulative Distribution Function

We wish to randomly sample the cumulative distribution function of the pixel occupation number to generate a galaxy map. The theoretical power spectrum is read in using the same interface as the one used for the CMB analysis. We set the total number of galaxies in the simulation, the pixelisation scheme (n_{side}) and the maximum multipole (l_{max}). l_{max} is restricted to a maximum of $2 * n_{side}$ due to Nyquist theorem. Initially we set $n_{side} = 16$, since it's more computationally viable to work with low resolution data to begin with. Table 1 gives the value for the number of pixels and the average number of galaxies for different resolutions and different n_{sides} .

The algorithm for generating this from the input power spectrum is as follows:

- Generate the signal realizations using a random number seed from the input power spectrum
- Convert the delta map into a galaxy number map using the transformation $\delta N_i = \frac{N_i - \bar{N}}{\bar{N}}$ which gives $N_i = \bar{N} * (\delta N_i + 1)$ where i goes from 0 to n_{pix} , the total number of pixels in the map.
- Now we reproduce the map by using a random sampling method to reassign a number of galaxies to each pixel bin. Firstly, we generate a cumulative distribution of galaxies cdf_N such that the k^{th} pixel has a total of $\sum_{i=0}^k N_i$ galaxies. This would mean that for $i = n_{pix}$, $N_i = N_{tot}$, where N_{tot} is the total number of galaxies which in this case is 10^7 . We normalize this distribution by dividing each member by N_{tot} . This gives us an array of n_{pix} numbers which range between $0 < \frac{N_i}{N_{tot}} < 1$.
- We use a uniform random number generator to give us an array of N_{tot} random numbers between 0 and 1. For each random number, we find the pixel value for which the difference between the random number and $\frac{N_i}{N_{tot}}$ is minimum. We then assign a galaxy into this pixel. Thus, the $\frac{N_i}{N_{tot}}$ galaxies are arranged into an array of size n_{pix} with an average of

\bar{N} . We then convert this into a δN_i , which gives us a map of sampled overdensities.

In order to verify that the sampling process gives us an expected galaxy map, we compare the maps obtained before and after the sampling process. We also see whether the auto power spectrum of the a_{lm} 's before and after sampling gives us a C_l value close to the theoretical value.

Figure 3.1: **Red**:The theoretical power spectrum to $l = 32$. **Blue**: The pseudo-spectrum estimate before the random sampling and **Green**: estimates after random sampling. This shows that the simulated map from the random sampling returns the values of the original (theoretical) power spectrum.

To confirm that the overdensities obtained after the sampling give us the required distribution. we converted the final N_i 's into δN_i 's and plotted the histogram, we see that the distribution is gaussian, which is what we expect for galaxies. For our analysis, we started with a small number of galaxies 10^4 . This didnt give the required distribution since the signal to noise was too low and the mean value \bar{N} was about 1.

3.3 Method 2: Generating a Poisson Distribution

An alternate method to generate a galaxy count map from a set of input C_l 's is by drawing Poisson variables for each pixel. This methods has been used in

Figure 3.2: **Left:** Initial overdensities from the input power spectrum **Right:**Final Overdensity estimates. We see that the final overdensities give us the expected gaussian distribution, which also corresponds with the initial distribution.

previous studies of clustering in SDSS data (Blake et al. (2004), Padmanabhan et al. (2007). In Blake et al. (2005), they take $n_{side} = 32$ and $\sim 10^5$ galaxies to generate a Poisson distribution. To create a Poisson distribution from the fiducial coefficient values we use the following algorithm

- Set $\lambda = N_i$, where N_i is the number of galaxies in the i^{th} pixel. This is obtained by converting the signal from the theoretical power spectrum δN_i into N_i by using $(\delta N_i + 1) * \bar{N}$.
- Set $L = exp(-\lambda)$. Initialize the probability to be 1 i.e. $p=1$ and set a variable $k=0$.
- While p is greater than L , generate a uniform random number, u , and set p as $p * u$. Increment k for each iteration.
- Return $k-1$, this will be the Poisson random variable for the given pixel. Generate n_{pix} random variables.

The final array will be a distribution of galaxies. We use the formula, as in the previous method, to convert this into an overdensity. On comparing the overdensity with a sufficiently high number of galaxies, we get histogram plots that are very similar and the autopowerspectra return the theoretical values.

We generated 1000 mock realisations to draw Poisson variables from. We then estimated the auto power spectrum, plotted the mean and variance of the C_l 's to see whether the realisation was return the input power spectrum. We used high resolution simulations for the mock realisations. the figure ?? shows the resultant power spectrum with $n_{side} = 128$.

3.4 Comparing the Methods

In this section we compare the two methods for generating simulated galaxy maps. Figure 3.4 shows a comparison of the power spectrum estimates from both methods. We see from the figure that both methods return similar estimates.

Figure 3.3: For $n_{side} = 16$, the Poissonian realization of overdensities. The galaxies are assigned to pixels using the algorithm for generating the variables and then converted to overdensities. This realisation is like the initial density fluctuations of the signal from the theoretical power spectrum.

Moreover, the δ maps from both methods return values close to the initial overdensities, thus, we can say that both methods give valid results.

In our analysis of simulated data, we use Method 2: Generating a Poisson distribution. This method has been used in previous work like Blake et al. [2004], Padmanabhan et al. [2005] and Thomas et al. [2011]. This method is also preferred since it is computationally viable. For method 1, it takes ~ 3 minutes to run a low resolution simulation with $N_{side}=16$ and $N_{tot} = 10^6$, thus, making it unfeasible for high resolution simulations.

Figure 3.4: The figure shows the noise power spectrum for different \bar{N} . The red line shows the input C_l 's. The green line corresponds to $\bar{N} = 1$. We see that the noise power spectrum coefficients have a higher value than the signal. Thus, this value of \bar{N} cannot be used for estimation. The blue line corresponds to $\bar{N}=3$, where we can see that after $l \sim 80$, the SNR is lower than 1, thus, it is not a feasible for high l 's. The black line corresponds to $\bar{N}=5$. We can see that for most l 's till 128, the SNR is high. $\bar{N}=10$ and $\bar{N}=50$ are shown in gold and purple respectively.

3.5 Analysis of Noise

In this section, we analyse the noise properties of the galaxy maps. Firstly, assuming the noise to be a Poisson process, with $\lambda = \bar{N}$, we estimate the power spectrum for different \bar{N} . For each \bar{N} , this gives an indication for the angular scales at which the signal to noise (SNR) is greater than 1.

We also plot the resulting pixel count distributions in Figure 3.5. We find that for high \bar{N} the distribution resembles a Gaussian with the same mean and standard deviation. However, at low \bar{N} there is a stark difference in the distributions. Since the likelihood for GHS is a Gaussian, we expect the sampler to run into problems in the low \bar{N} regime.

Next, we calculate the difference between the weighted mean of the N_l 's and the shot noise term given by $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{\bar{N}}$.

The expression for calculating the weighted mean is as follows is given as follows

$$\bar{N}_l = \frac{\sum_l N_l * (2l + 1)}{\sum_l 2l + 1} \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.5: **Left:** Comparing the distribution of noise for $N_{side}=128$, at $\bar{N} \sim 50$ and **Right:** $\bar{N} \sim 0.5$ with a Gaussian distribution same mean and standard deviation.

$$E = \bar{N}_l - \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N} \quad (3.2)$$

Table 3.1: The table shows the values for the expression in (3.2) for different values of \bar{N} and n_{side}

N_{side}	0.1	0.5	1	5	10	50
64	$-3.03 * 10^{-6}$	$-5.44 * 10^{-6}$	$-5.5 * 10^{-7}$	$-9.4 * 10^{-8}$	$-3.4 * 10^{-8}$	$-2.04 * 10^{-7}$
128	$-6.4 * 10^{-6}$	$-3.08 * 10^{-6}$	$1.1 * 10^{-6}$	$1.35 * 10^{-7}$	$-2.17 * 10^{-8}$	$-2.05 * 10^{-7}$
256	$-5.5 * 10^{-7}$	$-5.5 * 10^{-8}$	$-1.44 * 10^{-7}$	$-8.02 * 10^{-8}$	$-5.4 * 10^{-9}$	$-3.15 * 10^{-7}$
512	$-6.16 * 10^{-8}$	$-1.92 * 10^{-7}$	$-3.615 * 10^{-7}$	$-2.12 * 10^{-7}$	$-6.25 * 10^{-8}$	$-7.8 * 10^{-8}$

For different \bar{N} and N_{side} , we see that the value of E is close to 0. Thus, we know that the noise power spectrum weighted mean has the same value as the constant shot noise term. However, due to the small differences from 0, we want to investigate whether there is a regime in which we find a deviation from 0.

Our aim is to look at the difference between N_l and the shot noise term, to see whether the shot noise can be expressed as $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$. In the following subsections, we detail the methods for calculating $Z(l)$ and the χ^2 tests for analysing the significance of the resulting power spectra. $Z(l)$ is defined by

$$Z(l) = N_l - \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}. \quad (3.3)$$

3.5.1 Methods for Calculating $Z(l)$

1. $Z(l)$ is estimated as the difference between $N(l)$ and $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$. $N(l)$ is the scale dependent noise, given as the difference between the theoretical and estimated C_l 's

$$Z(l) = C_l - C_l^{est} + \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N} \quad (3.4)$$

Where C_l^{est} is the average of the estimated C_l 's. We run 10^5 simulations so that the result doesn't show effects specific to one realisation.

2. *Unclustered Data*: We evaluate the same expression for $Z(l)$ but with C_l 's set to 0, i.e. with a randomly distributed map of galaxies. The aim is to see whether an deviation produced is a result of the galaxy clustering.
3. Instead of keeping the shot noise term fixed as $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$, we make it scale dependent. We take the input galaxy map with N_i galaxies per pixel and from it generate a noise map with $\sqrt{N_i}$ galaxies per pixel. We proceed to estimate the noise C_l 's and replace it for the shot noise term in the expression for $Z(l)$.

Figure 3.6: $Z(l)$ estimates calculated from Method 1, from the mean of 10^5 realisations. In order to see whether the estimates are centered around 0, we take very low values of \bar{N} . We see that the $Z(l)$ values look to be centered around 0.

In figure 3.6, we see that the $Z(l)$ plot looks to be centered around 0. We observe that for lower \bar{N} , the scatter in the $Z(l)$ values is greater. This is due to

the fact that the input maps contain lesser number of galaxies and therefore, at individual l 's, we find that $Z(l)$ deviates from 0. We can see, most prominently for $\bar{N}=0.01$ that at low l 's, the plot is not centered around 0. We investigate this further in the next subsection with χ^2 tests.

3.5.2 χ^2 tests

We want to find whether the scatter of the noise C_l 's is centered around 0 after applying the shot noise correction $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$. The error on the value of $Z(l)$ is given by equation 3.5

$$\Delta Z(l) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{2l+1}} \left(C_l + \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N} \right) * \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{sim}}} \quad (3.5)$$

In order to see whether the $Z(l)$ scatter is centered around 0, we plot the $\chi^2(c)$ value versus c , where c is a constant and the $\chi^2(c)$ is given by

$$\chi^2(c) = \sum_l \left(\frac{Z(l) - c}{\Delta Z(l)} \right)^2 \quad (3.6)$$

We keep the l for summation as flexible. Initially, it is kept as l_{max} , which in this case is 128. On plotting χ^2 values with a large step size for c , we find there to be no deviation of the minimum from 0. However, when we reduce the step size and resolve the plot in finer detail, we can see that χ^2 is minimum at a value of c that differs significantly from 0.

From the top panel of figure 3.7, we can see that for large step size the χ^2 plot is centered around 0. However, the bottom panel for c_{min} as a function of l_{max} , with a higher resolution by decreasing step size, we find that there is a significant deviation from 0 at low l and a marginal deviation at high l 's too.

3.6 Summary and Discussion

In this chapter, we have described two methods for generating simulated galaxy clustering data. We find, from the power spectrum estimates at $N_{side} = 16$, that the two methods return similar estimates and are equivalent. Therefore, we can use either method for our analyses and choose to use the method of drawing Poisson variables, since it is computationally more viable.

We also analyse the noise in the data. Assuming the noise to be a Poisson process, we create a distribution with $\lambda = \bar{N}$ and see the characteristics of the resulting auto power spectrum. We find that the noise C_l 's are centered around 0, after applying the correction term $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$.

Figure 3.7: **Top:** The plot shows the χ^2 values versus the constant c , for different \bar{N} . *Blue:* $\bar{N}=50$, *Pink:* $\bar{N}=5$, *Black:* $\bar{N}=1$, *Gold:* $\bar{N}=0.1$. **Bottom:** The value of c for which χ^2 is minimum is plotted against the maximum l to which the χ^2 values are added. Even for high $\bar{N} \sim 50$, we see a significant deviation from 0. The green line is the clustered measurement from the theoretical C_l 's, whereas, the blue line presents the measurements for a randomly distributed galaxy map.

We then look at different methods to calculate the noise N_l and subsequently, $Z(l)$ to see whether the estimates are centered around 0 at low \bar{N} and whether $\frac{\Delta\Omega}{N}$ can describe the shot noise term. We perform χ^2 tests and find that there is a significant deviation of χ^2 values from 0, especially, when only the lower l 's are added in the calculation.

Chapter 4

Analysis of Simulated Galaxy Clustering Data

4.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter we introduced the different methods for simulating galaxy maps from theoretical C_l 's. In this chapter we analyse the power spectrum estimates using Guided hamiltonian Sampling and the difference in estimates with varying signal to noise (SNR).

Firstly, we provide a justification for conducting our tests in harmonic space. Previous studies have shown that for large galaxy redshift surveys that probe massive cosmic volumes, it is more feasible to work with power spectrum coefficients, as opposed to the galaxy correlation function. The following presents a summary for why we perform spherical harmonic analysis (SHA) akin to the work done in the CMB community.

- C_l provide a statistical measure where there is no loss of phase information. This is crucial for probing large cosmic volumes, since most statistical measures lose the radial information in redshift surveys. Other measures like the two-point correlation function tell us nothing about underlying texture like filamentary structure etc. This is a problem with other methods like counts-in-cells too (Saunders et al. [1991]).
- The matrix for power spectrum coefficients is highly uncorrelated. Thus, inversion processes are not computationally intensive.
- Since our aim is to measure $P(k)$ i.e. the underlying 3-D matter power spectrum, it is easier to go from C_l 's to $P(k)$ than from $w(\theta)$

Tegmark et al. [2001] provides a complete analysis of why SHA is used for early SDSS galaxy data. It is argued in the paper that for large scales (low l 's) a C_l analysis is more effective. A companion paper, Connolly et al. [2001] uses $w(\theta)$ as the statistical measure. Arguments in Tegmark et al. [2001] are based on the work from Scharf and Lahav [1993] (SHA applied to the 2-Jy redshift survey), Baugh and Efstathiou [1993] and Huterer et al. [2000] which analyzes data from edinburgh/durham south galaxy catalog. SHA had fallen out of favour since it was inapplicable on the small-sized datasets available before the '90's. Scharf and Lahav [1993] provide a list of advantageous features of SHA, for eg. SHA connects small angular scales (high l 's) to large scale information and it also acts as a data compression, as large maps are compressed to few coefficients. These papers were a result of expansive galaxy surveys like IRAS, which led to a resurgence of the work pioneered by Hauser and Peebles [1973].

In this chapter we aim to compare two methods for estimating C_l 's, namely Guided Hamiltonian Sampling and pseudo C_l . The structure of the chapter is as follows: in section 4.2 we apply GHS to high signal to noise simulations. In section 4.3 we investigate how the sampler behaves in low SNR and the regime in which the estimates are biased. Lastly, in section 4.4 we compare the results to the pseudo C_l estimates, as described in Appendix B.

4.2 High Signal to Noise Data

After making maps with different resolutions, and estimating the power spectrum using pseudo- C_l to see whether the theoretical values were returned by the simulation process, our aim was to apply the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler to the data. We, intially, apply the method to low resolution $N_{side} = 16$ data to see whether we get the input C_l 's back after estimation.

We want to use GHS to estimate the power to high l 's, i.e. small scales. Thus, we increase the resolution of the input maps. We investigate the performance of the sampler with high N_{side} . We find that the sampler takes 12 hours to converge for $N_{side}=256$ and a few days for $N_{side}=512$. This is impractical for running the sampler several times on maps with different properties. Therefore, we work with $N_{side} = 128$ to analyse the affects of changing properties of the map. Table 4.2 summarizes the properties of the map used as input to the sampler.

For the input beam to the sampler we want an array consisting of N_{pix} number of 1's. For this we set the full width at half maximum to be equal to 0. Preliminary analysis is done without applying data masks. For low resolution data, the sampler converges quickly, taking only ~ 3000 samples, at an acceptance rate of 0.9. At $N_{side} = 128$, the sampler takes about 1 hour and 7600 samples to converge at an accepctance rate of 0.6. These characteristics are similar to the sampler's performance with CMB data of the same N_{side} .

Figure 4.1: The figure shows $\log C_l$ versus l for different \overline{N} in high SNR regime. We can see a correspondence between the estimated and the theoretical value. **Red:** $\overline{N}=50$, **Green:** $\overline{N}=20$, **Blue:** $\overline{N}=10$.

Characteristics	Value
N_{side}	128
l_{max}	128
N_{tot}	10^7
\overline{N}	50.8

Table 4.1: the table shows the properties of the high resolution map sampled using GHS

Comparing the GHS estimates to the theoretical values, we see that the mean of the samples overestimates the C_l 's at low l 's. In order to find the cause of this overestimation, we first make 100 different realisations of the input map. We observe that for all realisations, the mean overestimates the C_l . This implies that the mean is not the appropriate statistic for finding the best estimate of the C_l . We plot the individual distributions of the C_l samples, along with the theoretical value and the mean.

From figure 4.2 we can compare the distributions at low and high l 's. At $l = 2$ the distribution of C_l samples is not symmetric about the mean, thus the peak of the distribution doesn't coincide with the mean. Since the distribution of C_2 is an inverse gamma, the mean is greater than the mode. We can see that this problem doesn't come about at high l where the samples have a Gaussian distribution. In Appendix C, we look at an alternate statistic of using mode $\pm 68\%$ confidence level.

Figure 4.2: *Left*: The distribution of samples for C_2 . We can see that it is not symmetric about its peak. *Right*: The distribution of samples for C_{128} . We see that the samples have a Gaussian distribution.

Table 4.2: The table shows the number of samples required for convergence when the data is masked

Mask size(radian)	Number of Samples	Acceptance Rate
0.15	4500	0.85
0.5	7000	0.83
0.8	10000	0.80
1	14000	0.75
1.2	30000	0.7

4.2.1 Dealing with Data Masks

Galaxy redshift surveys only cover a part of the sky. We require data masks to simulate the region of the sky covered by the survey of interest. In this part of the analysis, we look at the different kinds of data masks and how they affect sampler performance. Similar to the analysis for CMB simulated maps, we use symmetric masks as a starting point to look at acceptance rate and number of samples for convergence.

From table 4.2, we see that the acceptance rate doesn't decrease very much with masked area. However, the number of samples does increase substantially. Since the area masked by the largest symmetric mask is similar to the amount of sky coverage of most redshift surveys, we know that GHS will take ~ 30000 samples for simulated data with the SDSS mask. With large masks, we find that the a_{lm} 's are highly correlated and take very long to converge. Since our aim is to estimate the power spectrum, we stop the sampler once the C_l 's have met the Hanson criterion.

4.3 Low Signal to Noise Data

In section 4.2, we apply GHS to high SNR data and see that it returns the fiducial C_l values and is, therefore, a valid method in the high SNR regime. We would now like to see the performance of GHS in low SNR regime. Since some surveys have a low number of average galaxies per pixel, for $N_{side} = 128$ or higher, testing GHS at low \bar{N} is useful for knowing whether the method is applicable to those surveys.

At low SNR, we see that the data no longer has a Gaussian distribution. We can see the the difference in the distributions in Figure 3.5, where we analyse the noise in different regimes.

Figure 4.3: The figure shows the GHS estimates of the C_l 's for three different \bar{N} 's **Red**=0.5, **Green**=2, **Blue**=3.5. The plot is in log scale to discern whether the estimates are biased.

From figure 4.3 that at $\bar{N}=2$ and 3.5, the theoretical estimates are returned by GHS. However, at even lower \bar{N} values of 0.5, there is a bias in the estimates from GHS, since all the C_l 's highly overestimated.

4.4 Comparing Estimation Methods

In this section we compare the estimates obtained from GHS to the estimates we get in Appendix B from pseudo C_l estimation. We look at the GHS samples in the high SNR regime, where we observe no bias. The characteristics of the data are presented in Table.

From figure 4.4 we see that the ratio of error bars estimated from GHS

Figure 4.4: The ratio of errors from GHS and PCL estimates is plotted as a function of l . The anomalous peak at $l=9$ is due to the fact that both methods overestimate the C_l at that scale.

and pseudo C_l is centered about 1. Since the samples of C_l obtained from GHS at low l don't have a symmetric distribution, we take the mean of the upper and the lower error. The error for the PCL estimates is calculated using the analytic expression for full sky simulations.

There is a peak at $l = 9$. At this multipole, both methods overestimate the C_l and therefore, the error ratio is not close to 1. The reason for both methods overestimating the C_l value is still unclear.

4.5 Summary and Discussion

In this chapter we looked at the application of GHS for the first time to simulated galaxy clustering data. We evaluated the C_l 's at different SNR and found that GHS returns the fiducial values.

We demarcate the region in which GHS gives unbiased estimates from the region where GHS has a bias. The bias is due to the distribution of galaxies deviating from a Gaussian.

We compare GHS estimates to C_l 's from pseudo spectrum methods and find that the ratio of errors is centered around 1. This shows an agreement between the two methods of estimation.

Chapter 5

Application of GHS to Cosmological Datasets

5.1 Introduction

After having analysed simulated data with GHS, we would like to apply the method to observed galaxy catalogs from massive redshift surveys. Originally, galaxy surveys would measure redshifts spectroscopically. Since, this requires a lot of integration time to measure the spectra, and we need a large number of galaxies in a wide range of redshifts to probe a large cosmic volume, it is impractical to measure redshifts from spectra for such a large number of galaxies. To overcome this hurdle, broad-band photometric filters are used to estimate redshift from overall flux. This technique has been used prolifically with SDSS and has led to the creation of large samples of luminous red galaxies. Photometry is also used for calculating redshifts in current surveys like Dark Energy Survey (DES) and the proposed method for future ground and space-based probes like EuCLiD, LSST, JWST etc.

The structure of this chapter is as follows. In section 5.2, we introduce the MegaZ DR7 data and the method reducing the catalog to a sample of $\sim 700,000$ galaxies. We then explain the procedure to convert the catalog to a galaxy overdensity map. In section 5.3, we analyse the estimates in each of the redshift bins and look at the distributions of the individual C_i 's. We analyse the systematics arising from the data and the estimation method, providing a summary of how they have been dealt with in the literature. We then move onto other datasets like DES (section 5.5) and BOSS (sections 5.6 and 5.7). We provide a summary and discussion in section 5.8.

5.2 MegaZ DR7 Data

Galaxy redshift surveys return large datasets with information about the large scale structure of the universe. Current and recently concluded surveys include 2dF, 2MASS, CFHT, UKIDSS, PanSTARRS etc. In this project, we apply the guided hamiltonian sampler to data from the SDSS MegaZ DR7 survey of galaxies between redshifts of 0.45 and 0.65. This data catalog is an updated version of the MegaZ DR4 (Collister et al. [2007]) and contains ~ 1.5 million galaxies. They are old, red elliptic galaxies that provide a clean and consistent sample. They have a uniform spectral energy distribution (SED) characterised by a sharp discontinuity at 4000 Å. These properties of the luminous red galaxies (LRG's) make them very useful for cosmological analysis.

LRG's have been used in several studies like Hirata et al. [2004], Eisenstein et al. [2005a] and in the detection of the baryon acoustic peak in the galaxy autocorrelation function (Eisenstein et al. [2005b]). Obtaining large number of precise redshifts from LRG's through spectroscopy is an arduous task. An alternative is proposed in Csabai et al. [2003] using photometry from multiple filters. The motivation is that the decrease in accuracy of the redshift is offset by the large number of galaxies for which the information can be obtained over a wide area, encompassing a large cosmic volume. The nature of these LRG's makes them ideal for the application of photometric redshift algorithms, having an accuracy of $\sigma_z \sim 0.03$. For the MegaZ data, an artificial neural networks code (ANNz) is used for redshift measures from the multi-band colours (Collister and Lahav [2004]). It has been used for estimates with DR4 and DR7 data. Upcoming surveys which will return huge datasets like LSST, EUCLID will be using the technique of photometric redshifts.

The uncut MegaZ catalog contains ~ 1.5 million LRGs. It is truncated using selection cuts for redshift, colour, M-star contamination and angular selection function for SDSS DR7 coverage from *tsChunk.dr7.best.par* available from www.sdss.org/dr7/coverage. The criteria for selection are as follows:

- We use a redshift range of $0.45 < z < 0.65$. Galaxies within this range are divided into bins of $\Delta z = 0.05$.
- Colour selection includes 2 cuts. First, we impose a restriction of $d_{perp} \geq 0.55$ where and $i_{dev} \leq 19.8$. These cuts have been used for the 2SLAQ sample too.
- M-star contamination is problematic since M-stars can comprise $\sim 5\%$ of the sample, owing to similar broadband colours. The ANNz code gives an output δ_{sg} which is the probability that an object is a galaxy. It ranges from 'guaranteed star' 0 to 'guaranteed galaxy' 1. We remove all objects with $\delta_{sg} < 0.2$, which reduces contamination to $\sim 1.5\%$ with a minimal loss of LRGs.

A more detailed study of these selection cuts can be found in T11] for SDSS DR7 and Blake et al [2007] for earlier releases of MegaZ-LRG data.

In order to convert a galaxy catalogue of RA and Dec to a map N_i of galaxies with a resolution of i pixels, we use the following steps:

- The position of each galaxy (RA, Dec) is converted into a pair of angles on the sky (θ, ϕ) using the conversion $\theta = RA, \phi = -Dec + \frac{\pi}{2}$
- We use the Healpix function **ang2pix** to convert the pair of angles (θ, ϕ) into an index for the galaxy map
- The pixel corresponding to this index is incremented. The final map is written to a .fits file. , a format that can be easily read into the sampler.
- We set the resolution as per our requirements by defining n_{side} .

The map-making function is flexible with just resolution and position of the objects required. We can use this program for making maps of stars too.

5.2.1 Dealing with Masks

Data masks account for unobserved pixels and the angular selection function of the survey. For our analysis of SDSS data, we use the mask for the MegaZ DR7 data provided in T11. For the initial low resolution analysis, we degrade the $N_{side}=1024$ mask to an $N_{side}=16$ mask and for the final analysis, to an $N_{side}=128$ mask. For degrading the mask, using the IDL routine **udgrade**, part of the Healpix IDL routines which are publicly available. The routine can be used to either upgrade or degrade the resolution of an input map. Healpix maps exist in one of two schemes, 'RING' or 'NESTED', the descriptions are given in Gorski et al. [2005]. They are distinguished by their pixel ordering and thus produce completely different maps from the same array of data. **udgrade** output a mask in 'NESTED' scheme, whereas the map from the catalog is in the 'RING' scheme. We use the **swapscheme** routine to convert the mask to a map of 'RING' scheme.

Degradation decreases the number of pixels and increases the pixel size (keeping total area constant). The map is degraded by averaging the pixel values in a region of the high resolution map and assigning the value to a pixel of larger size in the map with lower resolution. Therefore, certain pixels, after degradation, contain values between 0 and 1 (this can be seen in the right panel of Figure 5.2.1). In order to prevent any bias from this region, we set all pixels with value <1 , to 0. From the figure, we can see that this doesn't lead to much of a loss of area.

Figure 5.1: **Left:** The MegaZ DR7 mask showing areas of coverage. **Right:** The degraded mask to $n_{side} = 16$. We can see that there is a gradient between 0 and 1 that is created as a result of the degradation. We make it a binary mask by setting all values less than 1 to 0.

Table 5.1: The table shows the number of samples required for convergence when the data is masked, with varying dimensionality scaling factor.

η	Number of Samples	Acceptance Rate
0.1	117000	1
0.3	43000	0.9
0.5	36000	0.85
1	23000	0.7

5.3 Estimation with MegaZ DR7 data

After applying the sampling methods on the simulated data, we aim to use GHS on the SDSS DR7 data. The galaxy catalogue is converted into a **Healpix** map. This map is read into the sampler and converted into an overdensity map using $\delta = \frac{N_i}{N} - 1$. We use one of the signal realizations as input to the sampler for the \hat{C}_l 's using the theoretical power spectrum. The figure shows the estimated power spectrum using the Bayesian confidence interval at 68% level.

We start with low resolution maps of SDSS galaxies. We degrade the mask to the required resolution and analyse the output C_l 's. We also look at the sampler performance with changes in the dimensionality scaling factor (η).

We see that there is no change in the estimated power spectrum even after changing the dimensionality scaling factor, η for the GHS. However, there is a change in the acceptance rate and the number of samples required for convergence (see Table 5.1).

After applying GHS to low resolution data to see whether the sampler converges, we increase the resolution to $N_{side}=128$ so that we can sample to higher l 's. We split the sample into four redshift bins like in T11 and apply GHS to each bin individually.

Since the sampler requires a starting point for the C_l 's, we input the theoretical power spectrum from Thomas et al. [2010] into our routine. The $P(k)$ for the power spectrum was calculated using CAMB (Lewis et al. [2000]). HALOFIT (Smith et al. [2003]) was then used to map the linear power spectrum into the non-linear regime at large l 's. A small angle approximation for $l \geq 60$ was used along with the full and exact window function, including the redshift space distortions. We can input the redshift of the galaxies into CAMB, thus, generating a theoretical power spectrum for each of the 4 redshift bins. The power spectrum extends to $l=500$ and is unbinned, therefore, has a C_l value for each l .

Figure 5.2: *Top Left*: The lowest redshift bin with $0.45 < z < 0.5$ shows a slight excess of power to $l=5$. *Top Right*: The second bin $0.5 < z < 0.55$ also shows a significantly high power at low l 's. At $l=8$, we see a slight excess with a very low error bar. *Bottom Left*: The third redshift bin $0.55 < z < 0.6$ has a point much above the theoretical value at $l=5$. *Bottom Right*: There is a hint of power in the highest redshift bin as well $0.6 < z < 0.65$.

Recent studies have shown an excess of power at the largest scales in estimated power spectra (Huterer et al. [2013], Ross et al. [2011], [2012a] and Thomas et al. [2010],[2011]). This excess can be attributed to several causes. One of the possibilities is an excess due to systematics at the largest scales. A treatment of the systematics and calibration can be seen in Leistedt

et al. [2013] where they use a quadratic maximum likelihood method (QML) on CMASS mock data catalogues for BOSS (Manera et al. [2013]).

The excess power can also be a manifestation of new physics like exotic dark energy, modified gravity or large scale inhomogeneity. This has profound implications for our understanding of which cosmological model best describes our universe. Similar observations of excess power from data, if returned by missions like DES, will lead to greater certainty of interesting new physics.

We also analyse the power spectrum of galaxies in different redshift bins between 0.45 and 0.65. In figure ??, we plot the power spectrum estimated using GHS over the theoretical C_l 's for the nearest redshift bin ($0.45 < z < 0.5$).

5.4 Analysis of Systematics

The estimation of power spectra can be affected by systematics effects arising from the sample of data or the method being applied. It is important to identify the sources of these systematics and model them for our analysis. We look at the possible causes for decrease in accuracy in the MegaZ data and in the Guided Hamiltonian Sampler in the estimates of the large scale structure power spectrum.

SDSS data has sample systematics arising from varying star-galaxy separation, seeing, overlapping survey stripes and brightness variation on the sky. In the earlier data release (Blake et al. [2007], MegaZ DR4), it is shown that these effects play an insignificant role in the estimation of the power spectrum. The paper also emphasizes the importance of photometric errors on LRG's, given their location on the galaxy luminosity function, $\phi(M)$, which describes the number of galaxies within an interval $[M, M + \delta M]$. The position of LRGs is where the gradient of ϕ is high, thus a small shift in M can create a large shift in the number of galaxies. Such a systematic effect, if correlated with sky position can lead to an artificial increase in power on those angular scales.

In Thomas et al. [2010], there is a detailed analysis of effects arising from extinction and redshift cross-correlation. The Milky way selectively absorbs light in the blue region of the spectrum, making objects appears redder. This leads to an imbalance in the colour selection process, and objects which aren't LRGs get mistaken for such. Since the reddening from our galaxy is a function of sky position, its harder to see statistical variations across the sky. This is resolved by using detailed galaxy dust maps and dereddening the model magnitudes *ugriz*. In a companion paper, Thomas et al. [2011] it is argued that the excess power is not a result of redshift estimation or extinction.

5.4.1 Systematics in GHS

GHS takes inputs from data maps, theoretical a_{lm} 's, realisation power spectra, noise matrix and beams. In our analysis with the LSS maps, both simulated and SDSS, we set the beam width to be 0, i.e. the beam is an array of 1's for each pixel. However, in reality, we know that the instrument beam is convolved with the a_{lm} 's, thus, we apply a gaussian beam with width related to the resolution of the data to smooth the signal realization.

The SDSS mask being used is a binary mask with a 0 assigned to each pixel. However, for the galaxies observed at the edge of the survey geometry, we see that the galaxies need to be weighted since their faintness causes instrumental error. We convolve a beam of appropriate width to the a_{lm} 's and reduce the area around the edges, thus, making a trade-off between the survey area and the instrumental systematics.

We can see that the M-star contamination in the galaxy catalog persists in the estimation process. An additional aspect of this contamination is in the estimation of the average galaxy number. We see that the \bar{N} for the noise matrix is higher due to the additional contamination from the M-stars. Thus, the noise matrix is not measured according to a pure sample of galaxies.

5.5 Dark Energy Survey (DES)

DES is a collaboration of 23 countries, which looks at 4 different probes of DE, namely, Type Ia supernovae, Galaxy clusters, Weak lensing, Baryon Acoustic Oscillation. It uses a powerful instrument, the DECam, atop the 4-m Blanco telescope in the Chilean mountains. DES has 2 blind cosmology catalogs, i.e. catalogs with no input cosmology being implemented, Aardvark and Buzzard. In this section we look at the Aardvark catalog, and generate a galaxy map from it.

The DES BCC galaxy catalog contains over 600 million entries and has 5 columns for ra, dec, shear1, shear 2 (lensing measurements) and redshift. In order to make the map out of this catalog, we split the file into 20 smaller catalogs and use the **Cat2Map** function which converts the data file into a map of specified N_{side} , which, in this case, we take as 128. We iteratively go through the files, converting ra, dec into pointings and the subsequent pointings into pixel indices. These maps corresponding to each catalog are stored in a single text file as pixel values. The pixel values values are added together and the final array of N_{pix} elements is saved in .FITS format. The figure shows the resultant map.

We can see from the figure and the input catalog that the value of \bar{N} is very high, ~ 3200 .

Figure 5.3: The figure shows the DES map for the Aardvark BCC catalog of 630 million galaxies. It is converted to a HealPix map using `Cat2Map` function.

5.5.1 Power Spectrum Estimation

The observation of excess power on the largest scales in studies like T11 point to a possibility of new and interesting physics. A similar observation of an excess of power in data from DES will provide corroborative evidence that the excess power is not a result of systematic effects, but indeed a manifestation of the underlying physics governing galaxy clustering.

After converting the galaxy catalog to a HealPix map, we create a data mask from this map. We assign the value 1 to pixels with observed galaxies and 0 to pixels with no observations. The mask and the map are input to the sampler to estimate C_l . The starting point C_l 's for the sampler are taken from theory and the first 3000 samples are 'burnt-in' in the estimation process. Unlike the case for MegaZ data, we don't have a theoretical power spectrum for the redshift distribution of the galaxies, hence, we use the burn-in method for C_l estimation

From the figure 5.4, we can see the estimated power spectrum for the DES BCC Aardvark catalog. On the largest scales, till $l \sim 7$, there is a marked excess of power when compared to the starting point C_l 's.

5.6 BOSS mock data

The CMASS sample of SDSS-III DR9 data has around a quarter of a million luminous red galaxies in the redshift range between $0.4 < z < 0.7$. In order to test estimation methods for clustering measurements, we require mock data of the sample.

In Manera et al. [2012] there are 600 mock catalogs published for this sample. They use a method which populates a 2nd order lagrangian perturbation

Figure 5.4: The power spectrum for the DES galaxy catalog is shown here, estimated using GHS. We can see that at the largest scales, there is a hint of excess power, possibly corroborating results from recent papers.

Table 5.2: Characteristics of the BOSS data catalog and the subsequent map are given in the table.

Characteristic	Value
N_{side}	64
N_{pix}	49152
l_{max}	128
NumGal	264283
\bar{N}	54

theory (2LPT) matter field, calibrating the mass of the DM halos by detailed comparison to N-body simulations. Halos are populated with mock galaxies using Halo Occupation Distribution (HOD) prescription, calibrated to produce clustering measurements on scales between 30 and 80 h^{-1} Mpc. The method is preferred for estimating the covariance matrix, since running large number of N-body simulations is computationally intensive. On the other hand having a low number (~ 50) simulations leads to a very noisy covariance matrix. These mocks have also been used to understand systematics in SDSS DR6 photometric quasar catalog (Leistedt et al. [2013]).

We see that with the percentage of sky coverage and the number of galaxies, the map has a high number of average galaxies per pixel. This means that the GHS estimates will be unbiased, as was seen with simulated data. We then apply the GHS to the map of the mock data.

The mask for sampling is created from the input data by setting pixels with observed galaxies as 1 and those without as 0.

Figure 5.5: The figure shows the estimated power spectrum from the BOSS CMASS sample of LRG's.

5.7 BOSS Data Catalog and Angular Power Spectrum

We analyse the galaxies observed by SDSS-III Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey, part of the SDSS DR9. SDSS DR9 includes redshifts for over 400,000 galaxies over an area of $3,275 \text{ deg}^2$. We look at the sample of galaxies between redshifts $0.4 < z < 0.7$ with a mean of $z=0.57$ (the CMASS sample). Details of the input map are given in Table 5.2. This is introduced in White et al. [2011] and Ross et al. [2011]. The definition of luminous red galaxies and the colour cuts is as follows

- $17.5 < i_{\text{cmod}} < 19.9$
- $r_{\text{mod}} - i_{\text{mod}} < 2$
- $d_{\text{perp}} > 0.55$
- $i_{\text{fiber2}} < 21.7$
- $i_{\text{cmod}} < 19.86 + 1.6*(d_{\text{perp}} - 0.8)$

where $d_{\text{perp}} = (r - i) - (g - r)/8 \sim (r - i)$. The "cmod" subscript denotes c-model magnitudes (an extensive discussion is in White et al. [2011]) and the

fiber2 subscript denotes the colour in the 2" spectroscopic fiber (Stoughton et al. [2002], Abazajian et al. [2004]). The angular power spectrum measurements for this dataset are provided in Anderson et al. [2012], which uses a sample of 264283 galaxies. Ross et al. [2011] presents a critical examination of the systematics in the CMASS sample. They demonstrate that the density of stars has a significant effect on the observed density of galaxies, and introduce spurious fluctuations in the density field. They suggest a weighting scheme to minimize these spurious fluctuations as a function of a given systematic effect.

5.8 Summary and Discussion

SDSS DR7 "MegaZ LRG" sample contains ~ 1.5 million luminous red galaxies, covering a region of 7746 deg^2 and a redshift range between 0.4 and 0.65. This provides a very large cosmic volume to work with. We apply standard colour and star-galaxy separation cuts to the catalog.

Upon applying GHS to the four different redshift bins, we find that there is an excess of power seen at the largest scales in each redshift bin, confirming the results from recent papers like Huterar et al. [2013], Ross et al. [2011], [2012a], Thomas et al. [2011]. On comparing our results to T11, we find that the best estimate C_l 's at low l 's ($l < 7$) is higher than the value for the lowest Δl bin in T11]. We also find that the error bars in our analyses are larger than those from T11.

We also apply GHS to other datasets, namely, DES and BOSS. From the DES galaxy number count map, we estimate the power spectrum coefficients and find that there is an observed excess on the largest scales.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The Guided Hamiltonian Sampler has been successfully applied to CMB data with a significant acceptance rate even for 10^6 dimensions at the highest pixelisation scheme. We see in this project that for a high density of galaxies, the sampler returns theoretical values of the power spectrum coefficients. We also look at the most efficient method for generating simulations and a comparative of pseudo spectrum methods with GHS. Lastly, we apply the sampler to observed galaxy catalogs

In the initial stages of the project, we applied the sampler to CMB simulations generated from WMAP7 input cosmology. We replicated the results from Balan et al. [2012] and found that the sampler works well under variations of different input parameters like beam size, noise level and the pixelisation scheme.

We generated full-sky simulated galaxy clustering maps from a theoretical power spectrum. We used two methods, namely, using the cumulative distribution function and drawing a Poisson variable. We find that the realisation power spectrum of the resulting overdensities returns the original C_l values and thus, we can say that both methods are valid for generating the simulations. We also compare the overdensities obtained to the initial fluctuations drawn from theory and find a correspondence between the two. The realisation power spectra from both methods are similar and therefore, we can use either of the two methods to generate the simulations for testing our method.

Upon looking at the noise power spectrum, we find that the noise scatter is centered around 0 after applying the correction term for the shot noise. We investigate the χ^2 statistic for noise power spectra with different \bar{N} and find that the minimum of the χ^2 deviates significantly from 0 at low \bar{N} and to a lesser extent at high \bar{N} . The plot for the constant value at which χ^2 is minimum versus the number of multipoles added for calculating the χ^2 shows a significant

deviation at low l , and a noticeable deviation at l_{max} .

We apply GHS to the simulated data at different signal to noise and find that the estimates return the fiducial values at high \bar{N} . At low SNR, we find that there is a bias in the estimates at $\bar{N}=0.5$, however, at the estimates do return the theoretical C_l 's. Comparing GHS estimates to pseudo C_l , we find that the ratio of errors is centered around 1, thus, showing a correspondence between the estimates from both methods.

Lastly, we apply GHS to published and unpublished galaxy catalogs. We look at the SDSS DR7 MegaZ data, analysed in T11. We confirm the excess power at the largest scales found in recent literature. We also look at the DES BCC catalog of $\sim 600million$ galaxies and estimate the power spectrum from the overdensity map. We can see a hint of excess power at the largest scales in the estimated power spectrum. We analyse BOSS mock data from Manera et al. [2012] and the catalog from SDSS DR9.

Appendix A

Theoretical Power Spectrum

For a random field $f(x)$ with zero mean, i.e. $\langle f(x) \rangle = 0$, the probability of realising a configuration is a *functional* $\text{Pr}[f(x)]$. For this field, we define a correlator (or correlation function) as the expectation value of the product of the field at different points in space. Thus, the two-point correlation function is

$$\xi(x, y) = \int df P[f] f(x) f(y) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

This is a functional integral or a path integral. Using the conditions from the cosmological principle of large scale homogeneity and isotropy, we obtain the constraint that ξ depends only on the spatial separation between the two points, i.e. $\xi(x, y) = \xi(|x - y|)$. We can repeat the argumentation for correlators in Fourier space. The field in k -space (where k is a characteristic length scale) is given by

$$f(k) = \int f(x) e^{-ik \cdot x} \frac{d^3x}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Using invariance of the correlator in Fourier space, we obtain

$$\langle f(k) f^*(k') \rangle = F(k) \delta(k - k') \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Thus, we can see that the Fourier modes are *uncorrelated*. A more detailed and rigorous treatment of the statistics of random fields in cosmology can be found in Challinor (2005) and Dodelson (2003).

To extract knowledge about the cosmology from the application of the estimation method to the LSS data, we need to compare the results to a power spectrum derived from theory. For this we need to connect the underlying 3D

mass distribution to the C_l . The formalism presented here follows the logic and notation from Padmanabhan et al. [2007], Huterer et al. [2001], Thomas et al. [2001], Tegmark et al. [2002], Blake et al. [2007].

The power spectrum is defined from the density contrast $\delta = \frac{\delta\rho}{\rho}$ of the galaxies using

$$\langle \delta(k)\delta^*(k') \rangle = (2\pi)^3 \delta^3(k - k') P(k) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The field decomposed into spherical harmonics is projected. We follow the same procedure for the theoretical power spectrum. Line of sight projection δ^{2D} is given by

$$\delta^{2D} = i^l \int \delta(k) W_l(k) \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The angular power spectrum coefficients can be defined as $C_l = \langle \delta^{2D} \delta^{*2D} \rangle$

$$C_l = 4\pi \int \Delta^2(k) W_l^2(k) \frac{dk}{k} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where $W_l(k)$ is a window function which absorbs the weight function of the projection. The spectrum has been recast into the dimensionless power spectrum.

$$\Delta^2(k) = \frac{4\pi k^3 P(k)}{(2\pi)^3} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The power spectrum can be written in terms of the galaxy power spectrum as

$$P_g(k) = b^2 P(k) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where b is the linear galaxy bias. For $l > 60$, the exact expression in equation (A.6) can be simplified using the small angle approximation (Blake et al. [2007])

$$C_l = b^2 \int P(k, z) \frac{n(z)^2}{x(z)^2} \left(\frac{dx}{dz}\right)^{-1} dz \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The expression underestimates the power at large scales and is therefore invalid. For large scales, even the equation (A.6) does not capture the true power spectrum below $l \sim 60$. This is due to boosting of the angular power spectrum by redshift space distortions.

Redshift Space Distortions: Small peculiar velocities not associated with the Hubble flow can cause distortion in the observed redshift of a galaxy. The *finger-of-god* effect, attributed to random velocity dispersion, is where long thin filaments in redshift space point directly back at the observer. The *Kaiser* effect is a more coherent effect which occurs in galaxies present in clusters, where they are drawn to the centre of mass and thus have a different redshift due to this peculiar velocity. This is a more subtle effect and thus more difficult to quantify. In redshift space this deviation alters the apparent clustering of galaxies, thus, the equation (A.6) underestimates the power in C_l .

Appendix B

Pseudo C_l Estimation

The method of summing over discrete galaxies in the incomplete sky was introduced in Peebles [1973]. It has been used in Hivon et al. [2001] for CMB data analysis and for the analysis of SDSS MegaZ data in T11. In this appendix, we look at the application of pseudo C_l estimation method to high resolution galaxy data. The code we use has been developed for an intensity mapping study (Wolz et al. [in prep])

Our first investigation is to see the effect of changing \bar{N} on the final estimate of C_l 's. Since \bar{N} is the average number of galaxies per pixel $\frac{N_{tot}}{N_{pix}}$, it gives a measure of the galaxy population in each pixel and the noise level of the simulation. We find that the C_l 's at low \bar{N} are biased at high l . Since $\bar{N} = \frac{N_{tot}}{N_{pix}}$ we reduce \bar{N} by increasing N_{pix} as well as by decreasing N_{tot} . We find that, it is only in the second case that there is any bias in the estimates

We attempt to remove this bias by applying the shot noise correction to these estimates. Thus, the corrected C_l 's are given by

$$C_l^{corr} = C_l - \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N} \tag{B.1}$$

which is equation 7 from T11. Here N is the total number of galaxies. We can see from the expression that the effect of having a smaller number of galaxies is mitigated by the shot noise term.

From Figure B.1, we can see that the estimated C_l 's return the theoretical values after correction for the shot noise term.

Figure B.1: The figure shows the mean pseudo C_l estimates for 10^5 realisations. The error measurement is given by the expression in (B.4) with $f_{sky}=1$. The theoretical C_l 's are plotted in blue.

B.1 Dealing with Masks

After experimenting with different input parameters on full-sky data, we use a data mask from a redshift survey to see how the retrieved estimates change. The previous chapter describes the SDSS MegaZ LRG DR7 mask. For our analysis with pseudo spectrum measurements, we use the SDSS mask.

The routine to calculate the PCL estimate requires Peebles correction values, I_{lm}, J_{lm} . These values are iteratively calculated for each l ($2l + 1$ of them) and the resulting files are concatenated into a single text file which is read in for converting a_{lm} 's to C_l 's. The I_{lm} and J_{lm} values are given by

$$I_{lm} = \int_{\Delta\Omega} Y_{lm}^* d\Omega \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$J_{lm} = \int_{\Delta\Omega} |Y_{lm}|^2 d\Omega \quad (\text{B.3})$$

We see that the estimates derived from the cut sky map follow the same shape as that of the input C_l 's, however, they are scaled up by a factor of 5. The different solid lines shows various factors that the C_l 's are scaled by. The error bars can be calculated using the analytic expression.

$$\sigma(C_l) = \sqrt{\frac{2C_l}{f_{sky} * 2l + 1}} \left(C_l + \frac{\Delta\Omega}{N} \right) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Appendix C

Bayesian Confidence Interval

Bayes' theorem for a parameter θ can be stated as follows

$$\Pr(\theta|d) = \frac{\Pr(d|\theta) \Pr(\theta)}{\Pr(d)} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

A confidence interval in Bayesian probability is the region of the posterior distribution of θ , given as $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ which contains a certain proportion of the posterior distribution mass. The extent of the interval determines the proportion of posterior mass included in the region. A parameter α denotes the tightness of the interval, i.e. the proportion of the posterior which is *excluded* from the interval. There will be more than one interval containing the same amount of posterior mass, thus, in order to get the interval we use one of the following methods

- **Highest Posterior Density(HPD)**: For a $(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence interval the HPD is the shortest interval $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ which contains $(1 - \alpha)$ and thus has the highest density of all such intervals.
- **Symmetric**: Alternatively, we can select the interval that is symmetric about its mode. For our analysis to obtain the best estimate of the C_l we use the highest posterior density since it can be used for any type of distribution function which doesn't have to be symmetric. This can be seen in the plot for C_2 where the distribution is an inverse gamma function and not a symmetric gaussian.

The algorithm for finding the HPD interval of given data at $(1 - \alpha)\%$ is as follows

Figure C.1: **Red Square:** The GHS estimates using Bayesian credible region. **Blue circle:** The estimates using mean and standard deviation. **Solid line:** Theoretical coefficients. For $l = 2$, the standard deviation is very large and thus the error bar is not completely visible.

- The data array is sorted and the difference between the first element and the element at the desired level is taken as an initial value. For example, for an array with 100 elements at 68% confidence, the difference between the 0^{th} and 68^{th} elements is set as the initial value.
- The algorithm then moves iteratively over successive elements of the array taking the difference between the element and the corresponding value at a level of $i + 68$ (for 68% confidence).
- The minimum of these differences returns the values of the interval $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$
- In order to calculate the mode of this interval we take an HPD with a very small level of confidence, which gives a small interval at the region of highest density. This is our best estimate and the difference between this value and one of the extrema of the intervals is the reliability which goes into plotting the power spectrum.

From figure C we can see that at low l 's there is a significant disparity in the best estimates calculated using the mean (blue) and those calculated using BCI (red). There is also a difference in the error bars from standard deviation and those from 68 % confidence level. We see that the estimates from BCI are closer to the true value and return smaller error bars. Thus, finding the highest posterior density is the preferred method for deducing the best estimate from GHS.

Bibliography

- Sreekumar Thaithara Balan. Bayesian methods for astrophysical data analysis. 2012.
- Julian Borrill. *arXiv:astro-ph/9712121v2*.
- Anthony Challinor. CMB anisotropy science : a review. (288):1–11, 2012.
- Mary Kathryn Cowles and Bradley P Carlin. Markov Chain Monte Carlo Convergence Diagnostics : A Comparative Review. 1996.
- S. Dodelson. *Modern Cosmology*. Academic Press, 2003.
- G Efstathiou. Myths and Truths Concerning Estimation of Power Spectra : The Case for a Hybrid Estimator. 000(February):1–27, 2008.
- Abate et al. Large Synoptic Survey Telescope: Dark Energy Science Collaboration. *arXiv:1211.0310v1*, pages 1–133, a.
- Balan et al. *arXiv:0805.3532*, 2008a.
- Bennett et al. Nine-Year Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) Observations: Final Maps and Results. pages 1–177, 1843.
- Bennett et al. Scientific results from the Cosmic Background Explorer (COBE). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 90(11):4766–73, June 1993. ISSN 0027-8424.
- Blake et al. Cosmological baryonic and matter densities from 600 , 000 SDSS Luminous Red Galaxies with photometric redshifts. 000(February), 2008b.
- Bond et al. Estimating the power spectrum of the cosmic microwave background. *Physical Review D*, 57(4):2117–2137, February 1998a. ISSN 0556-2821. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevD.57.2117. URL <http://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevD.57.2117>.
- Dunkley et al. Fast and reliable Markov chain Monte Carlo technique for cosmological parameter estimation. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 356(3):925–936, January 2005a. ISSN 00358711.

- Dunkley et al. Five-Year Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe Observations: Likelihoods and Parameters From the Wmap Data. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 180(2):306–329, February 2009a. ISSN 0067-0049.
- Eriksen et al. Power Spectrum Estimation from HighResolution Maps by Gibbs Sampling. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 155(2):227–241, December 2004. ISSN 0067-0049.
- Feroz et al. MultiNest: an efficient and robust Bayesian inference tool for cosmology and particle physics. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 398(4):1601–1614, October 2009b. ISSN 00358711.
- Gorski et al. On Determining the Spectrum of Primordial Inhomogeneity from the COBE 1 DMR Sky Maps : II . Results of Two Year Data Analysis. pages 1–13, b.
- Hivon et al. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 567, 1:2–17, 2002.
- Hobson et al. *Bayesian Methods in Cosmology*. Cambridge University Press, 2010a.
- Jasche et al. Bayesian power-spectrum inference for large-scale structure data. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 406(1):60–85, July 2010b. ISSN 00358711.
- Jewell et al. A Markov Chain Monte Carlo Algorithm for Analysis of Low Signal-To-Noise Cosmic Microwave Background Data. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 697(1):258–268, May 2009c. ISSN 0004-637X. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/697/1/258.
- Jones et al. A measurement of the angular power spectrum of the cmb temperature anisotropy from the 2003 flight of boomerang. 2005b.
- Larson et al. Seven-Year Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (Wmap) Observations: Power Spectra and Wmap -Derived Parameters. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 192(2):16, February 2011a. ISSN 0067-0049.
- Lentati et al. *arXiv:1210.3578*, 2012.
- Mandel et al. Type Ia Supernova Light-curve Inference: Hierarchical Bayesian Analysis In The Near-Infrared. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 704(1):629–651, October 2009d. ISSN 0004-637X.
- March et al. Improved constraints on cosmological parameters from Type Ia supernova data. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 418(4): 2308–2329, December 2011b. ISSN 00358711.
- Metropolis et al. *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 21, 1087, 1953.
- Mukherjee et al. A nested sampling algorithm for cosmological model selection. *arXiv:astro-ph/0508461v2*, 2006.

- Padmanabhan et al. The Clustering of Luminous Red Galaxies in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Imaging Data. (February), 2008c.
- Riess et al. Observational evidence from supernovae of an accelerating Universe. 1998b.
- Stompor et al. The MAXIMA Experiment : Latest Results and Consistency Tests. 2147(01):1–14, 2003.
- Watson et al. *arXiv:1010.0911*, 2011c.
- A. Gelman and D.B. Rubin. Inference from Iterative Simulation using multiple sequences. *Statistical Science*, Vol. 7, No. 4, 457–511, 1992.
- N. et al. Greisel. *arXiv: 1303.3005v1*, 2013.
- N.E. Groeneboom. *arXiv:0905.3823v1*, 2009.
- Kenneth M Hanson. *Proceedings of SPIE*, 467, 456, 2001.
- W. K. Hastings. *Biometrika*, 57, 97, 1970.
- P.J.E. Hauser, M.G. Peebles. *ApJ*, 185: 757–785, 1973.
- M.P Maisenger K. Hobson. Maximum-likelihood estimation of cosmic microwave background power spectrum from interferometer observations. *MNRAS* 334, 569–588 (2002).
- Wayne Hu and Martin White. The cosmic symphony. *Scientific American*, 290 (2):44–53, March 2004. ISSN 0036-8733.
- Wayne Hu, Daniel J Eisenstein, and Max Tegmark. Weighing Neutrinos with Galaxy Surveys. *arXiv:astro-ph/9712057v2*, 1997.
- Jens Jasche and Francisco S. Kitaura. Fast Hamiltonian sampling for large-scale structure inference. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 407 (1):29–42, September 2010. ISSN 00358711.
- E T Jaynes. Probability Theory : The Logic of Science. 1995.
- R Neal. Slice sampling. *The Annals of Statistics*, 31(3):705–767, 2003.
- Radford M Neal. An Improved Acceptance Procedure for the Hybrid Monte Carlo Algorithm *arXiv : hep-lat / 9208011v2* 20 Aug 1992. pages 1–16, 1992.
- Radford M Neal. Suppressing Random Walks in Markov Chain. (9508):1–22, 1995.
- Siang Peng Oh, David N Spergel, and Gary Hinshaw. *The Astrophysical Journal*.
- A.E. Raftery and S.M. Lewis. *Statist. Sci.*, 7(4):493–497, 1992.
- D.S. Sivia. *Data Analysis: A Bayesian Tutorial*. Oxford Science, 1996.

- J.S. Skilling. *Bayesian Analysis*. 1, 833.
- J. F. Taylor, M. a. J. Ashdown, and M. P. Hobson. Fast optimal CMB power spectrum estimation with Hamiltonian sampling. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 389(3):1284–1292, September 2008. ISSN 00358711.
- Jeremy F Taylor. The effect of foregrounds on observations of CMB polarization. (September), 2008.
- M Tegmark. Angular power spectrum of the 4-year COBE data. *arXiv:astro-ph/9601077v3*, 1996.
- Max Tegmark. Measuring Cosmological Parameters with Galaxy Surveys. *Physical Review Letters*, 79(20):3806–3809, November 1997. ISSN 0031-9007.
- S. A. Thomas, Filipe B Abdalla, and Jochen Weller. Constraining Modified Gravity and Growth with Weak Lensing . *arXiv:0810.4863v1*, 000(October), 2008.
- Shaun A Thomas, Filipe B Abdalla, and Ofer Lahav. The Angular Power Spectra of Photometric SDSS LRGs. 000(November), 2010.
- Surya T. Tokdar and Robert E. Kass. Importance sampling: a review. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics*, 2(1):54–60, January 2010. ISSN 19395108.
- Roberto Trotta. Bayes in the sky: Bayesian inference and model selection in cosmology. *arXiv:0803.4089v1*, (00):1–41, 2008.
- Benjamin D Wandelt, David L Larson, and Arun Lakshminarayanan. *arXiv : astro-ph / 0310080v2* 5 Oct 2003. pages 1–12, 2008.
- Benjamin D Wandelt, Frode K Hansen, and Anthony J Banday. The HEALPix Primer. *CM*(2), 2010.